

Breast Cancer Detection using Deep Learning

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Abstract—One of the dangerous diseases that affects women is breast cancer, for which there is currently no significant treatment. Deep learning techniques have been successfully applied in breast cancer detection since the introduction of artificial intelligence (AI), which has facilitated early diagnosis and hence increased patient survival rates. Deep learning requires less human interaction for equivalent feature extraction than standard machine learning algorithms. This paper offers a comprehensive assessment of the literature on deep learning-based techniques for breast cancer diagnosis, which can help researchers and practitioners better grasp the obstacles and emerging trends in the field.

The methods Sigmoid Activation function,min max scaler algorithm and label encoder which are more effective and accurate is used here

Keywords—*sequential model ,sigmoid activation function,label encoder,min max scaler,breast cancer detection.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of a cancer tumor results from aberrant cell proliferation that invades the surrounding tissues in the human body. The two primary types of tumors are benign and malignant, and a breast without a tumor is regarded as normal. Since benign tumor cells are non-cancerous, grow only locally, and are not contagious, they are not classified as incurable or extremely dangerous. However, malignant tumors are extremely dangerous since they are made of cancerous cells and can multiply rapidly, potentially spreading to different places of the body. It is anticipated that the number of deaths from breast cancer would rise to 27 million by 2030.

One benefit of deep learning is that it doesn't require any prior understanding of the data. Breast cancer detection is highly difficult because of the variety of features that are used, including radius, texture, perimeter, area, smoothness, compactness, concavity, symmetry, and fractal dimension. These features include radius, texture, perimeter, area, compactness, concavity, Concave Points SE, Symmetry SE, Fractal Dimension SE, Radius Worst, Texture Worst, Perimeter Worst, Area Worst, Smoothness Worst, Compactness Worst, Concavity Worst, Concave Points Worst, Symmetry Worst, and Fractal Dimension Worst.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The work by Nasser et al.[1] gives a thorough analysis of the deep learning methods used to detect breast cancer with the goal of enhancing early diagnosis and improving patient outcomes. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are the most widely used and accurate model in this field, according to the review, which determined this through a methodical examination of the literature. It emphasizes how important it is to use histopathological imaging and genetic data for efficient detection. The paper also highlights how crucial it is to use standardized assessment metrics—in particular, accuracy metrics—when evaluating model performance. It also talks about the datasets that are frequently used in studies to identify breast cancer, highlights major obstacles, and suggests future possibilities for study in the area. All things considered, the study is a useful tool for scholars and professionals who want to learn more and progress the subject of breast cancer diagnosis.

According to Abunasser et al.'s work [2], the paper highlights the incidence and mortality rates of breast cancer and addresses the disease's significant impact on global health. In 2020, 10 million deaths globally are expected to be attributable to breast cancer. The only ways to raise the current 30% to 50% survival rate are through early detection and effective diagnosis. The diagnosis and classification of breast cancer may be enhanced by leveraging technological advancements, particularly in deep learning. In order to identify and classify breast cancers, the study proposes the use of a deep learning model that considers eight distinct classes: benign adenosis, benign fibroadenoma, benign phyllodes tumor, benign tubular adenoma, malignant papillary carcinoma, malignant ductal carcinoma, and malignant lobular carcinoma.

The work by Khalid et al.[3] This work offers a thorough analysis of the body of research on deep learning-based methods for breast cancer detection. It emphasizes the value of approaches that have shown to be more effective and accurate in this field, such as the random forest algorithm, label encoder, and Sigmoid Activation function. This study seeks to provide academics and practitioners with a better knowledge of the developing trends and problems in deep learning-based breast cancer diagnosis by combining existing research findings. Further developments in this field could

lead to even better patient outcomes and diagnostic accuracy in the future.

The Adam et al.[4]work Enhancing the diagnostic precision of breast cancer by deep learning analysis of radiological images could ultimately result in better patient outcomes. This work conducted a thorough literature assessment of recent research on the use of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) in deep learning for breast cancer screening. Using Pubmed, a literature search was conducted from 2015 to December 31, 2022. Additional databases included pre-print depositories (like Research Square), Google Scholar, ACM Digital Library, Semantic Scholar, and Google search. Textures analysis and other non-deep learning articles were not included. PRISMA reporting criteria were applied.Examined several deep learning algorithms, analysis techniques, experimental designs, MRI picture kinds, ground truth types, sample sizes, quantities of benign and malignant lesions, and analysis results.

The Din et al. [5] This literature review critically analyzes past research on ML, DL, and Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) in BC classification and detection. It also explores publicly available datasets for different imaging modalities to facilitate future research. The review highlights the potential of AI-based techniques in enhancing BC diagnosis and precision medicine.

The study emphasizes the importance of earlier BC detection and the role of AI in leveraging large datasets for improved diagnostics. It discusses challenges, such as the limitations of DL approaches, and suggests avenues for future research in this emerging field of Medical Image Analysis (MIA) for BC detection.

III. METHODOLOGY

Before moving to the methodology ,it is imperative to import the required libraries and modules.The below mentioning libraries and modules are imported to facilitate data pre-processing,model construction,training,evaluating and predicting.

```
from keras.models import load_model
import pandas as pd
from matplotlib import pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
import numpy as np
```

A. DATA COLLECTION AND PREPARATION

The data set utilized is the Kaggle data set, which contains the various features. radius, texture, area, perimeter, smoothness, compactness, concavity, concave points, symmetry, and fractal dimension mean, as well as radius, texture, area, perimeter, area, compactness, concavity, and Concave Points, Symmetry, and Fractal DimensionWorst in

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11218622](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11218622)

ISBN: 978-93-5906-046-0@2024, Dept. of Computer Applications, Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, Kottayam

terms of radius, texture, perimeter, area, smoothness, compactness, concavity, concave points, symmetry, and fractal dimension of both the cancerous and benign cell included

```
file_path=r'C:\Users\saraj\OneDrive\Desktop\Breastcancer.csv'
df = pd.read_csv(file_path)
# Remove the 'Unnamed' column if it exists
df = df.loc[:, ~df.columns.str.contains('^Unnamed')]
print(df.describe().T)
print(df.isnull().sum())
#Rename Dataset to Label to make it easy to understand
df = df.rename(columns={'diagnosis':'label'})
print(df.dtypes)
#Understand the data
sns.countplot(x="label", data=df) #M - malignant B - benign
```

B. Splitting the dataset

With the help of the train split function from the sklearn.model selection module, the entire dataset was divided into two categories: training and testing.

```
#Split data into train and test to verify accuracy after fitting the model.
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split( "arrays: X, Y, test_size=0.25, random_state=42)
print("Shape of training data is: ", X_train.shape)
print("Shape of testing data is: ", X_test.shape)
```

C. Data Normalization

Normalization was done to ensure uniformity in scale across the dataset.

```
#Define the independent variables. Drop label and ID, and normalize other data
X = df.drop(labels = ["label", "id"], axis=1)
print(X.describe().T) #Needs scaling

#Scale / normalize the values to bring them to similar range
from sklearn.preprocessing import MinMaxScaler
scaler = MinMaxScaler()
scaler.fit(X)
X = scaler.transform(X)
print(X) #Scaled values
```

D. Building the Model

To build the model we have used the Sequential API from keras.

```
#Defining the model
model=Sequential() #makes it easier to add layers
model.add(Dense( units=16, input_dim=38, activation='relu')) #rectifiedlinearunit-activation(),16 dense layer
model.add(Dropout(0.2)) #dropping 20% of the data
model.add(Dense(1)) #adding another layer called dense layer with single output
model.add(Activation('sigmoid'))
```

E. Compiling the model

```
model.compile(loss='binary_crossentropy',optimizer='adam',metrics=['accuracy'])
print(model.summary())
```

F. Training and saving the Model

```
#fit with no early stopping or other callbacks
history=model.fit(X_train, y_train, verbose=1, epochs=100, batch_size=64, validation_data=(X_test, y_test))

# Assuming 'model' is your trained Keras model
model.save(r'C:\Users\saraj\OneDrive\Desktop\trained_model.h5')
```

IV. RESULT

A. USER INTERFACE VALUATION

This section provides the screenshot of the user interface of the application and demonstrates how it works. While we give the asked input the application detects whether there benign or malignant is present in that person.

Figure 1: image of the fields that we have to input the data with and the entered data

Figure 2: image of the fields that we have to input the data with and the entered data

Figure 3: image of the fields that we have to input the data with and the entered data

Figure 4: image of the fields that we have to input the data with and the entered data

Figure 5: The result

B. Model Performance Metrics

Figure 6: The matrix

C. Training the History Visualization

Showing the training and validation accuracy and loss at each epoch

Figure 7: Training and validation loss

Figure 8: Training and validation accuracy

The validation and training loss tends to reduce in each epoch ,The training and validation accuracy increases in each epoch.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, women's health is seriously threatened by breast cancer because there are limited therapeutic alternatives. Nonetheless, the advancement of deep learning techniques driven by artificial intelligence (AI) has revolutionized early detection of breast cancer and enhanced patient outcomes. Compared to conventional machine learning techniques, deep learning simplifies the diagnosis process.

The body of research on deep learning-based techniques for breast cancer diagnosis is thoroughly analyzed in this paper. It highlights the importance of methods like the sequential model,min max scaler, label encoder, and Sigmoid Activation function that have proven to be more precise and successful in this area. The purpose of this study is to increase the understanding of emerging trends and issues among scholars and professionals.

VI. REFERENCES

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